

Article

Floating Offshore Wind Farm Inter-Array Cabling Topology Optimisation with Metaheuristic Particle Swarm Optimisation

Sergi Vilajuana Llorente ¹
and José Luis Domínguez-García ^{1,*}

¹ Power Systems Group, Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, 2a, 08930 Sant Adrià de Besòs, Spain

² Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Jordi Girona 1-3, 08034 Barcelona, Spain

* Correspondence: jldominguez@irec.cat

Abstract

Floating offshore wind is now receiving much attention as an expansion to bottom-fixed, especially in deep waters with large wind resources. In this regard, improving the performance and efficiency of floating offshore wind farms (FOWFs) is currently a highly addressed topic. The inter-array (IA) cable connection is a key aspect to be optimised. Due to floating offshore wind (FOW) particularities such as dynamic cable designs, higher power capacities, and challenging installation, IA cabling is expected to be a primary cost driver for commercial-scale FOWFs. Therefore, IA cabling optimisation can lead to large cost reductions. In this work, an optimisation with an adaptive particle swarm optimisation (PSO) algorithm for such wind farms is proposed, considering the floating substructures' horizontal translations and its impact on the dynamic cable length. The method provides an optimised IA connection, reducing acquisition costs and power losses by using a clustered minimum spanning tree (MST) as an initial solution and improving it with the PSO algorithm. The PSO achieves a reduction in the levelised cost of energy (LCOE) between 0.018% (0.022 EUR/MWh) and 0.10% (0.12 EUR/MWh) and a reduction in cable acquisition costs between 0.18% (0.3 M EUR) and 1.34% (3.8 M EUR) compared to the initial solution, showing great potential for future commercial-sized FOWFs.

Keywords: floating wind; cabling optimisation; levelised cost of energy; dynamic cables; power losses; clustering; particle swarm optimisation

Academic Editor: Damien Guilbert

Received: 17 October 2025

Revised: 18 November 2025

Accepted: 24 November 2025

Published: 4 December 2025

Citation: Vilajuana Llorente, S.; Rapha, J.I.; Kallinger, M.D.; Domínguez-García, J.L. Floating Offshore Wind Farm Inter-Array Cabling Topology Optimisation with Metaheuristic Particle Swarm Optimisation. *Clean Technol.* **2025**, *7*, 110. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cleantechnol7040110>

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

There are certain reasons driving the continued research and development on floating offshore wind (FOW). The current efforts to replace fossil fuels with net-zero emission sources by 2050, aiming to limit temperature rise to 1.5 °C, contribute to the interest in its implementation [1]. Wind is one of the most installed renewable energies, along with hydropower and solar power, and offshore wind is already achieving high levels of efficiency in countries with significant potential, such as the United Kingdom and China, which are the two countries with the largest offshore wind power capacity installed. The capacity factors are reaching more than 50% in new offshore wind farms (OWFs) and between 30% and 45% in new onshore wind farms [2]. However, all commercial offshore wind projects are installed with bottom-fixed foundations, which is limited to zones with shallow waters (with announced projects indicating maximum depths of up to 65 m in

coming years [3]). This is due to their technical and economic limitations; as bottom-fixed foundations become massive, installation becomes challenging, and costs increase sharply in deeper waters. Yet around 80% of the world's offshore wind resource potential lies in deeper areas, where only FOW is feasible [4]. Furthermore, FOW presents fewer restrictions compared to bottom-fixed, e.g., land use, visual effect, and noise impact. Several countries do not present feasible areas for bottom-fixed due to their deep waters nearshore, resulting in rising interest in FOW.

According to [5], the inter-array (IA) cables represent up to a 9% of the total investment costs of an OWF. In floating offshore wind farms (FOWFs), IA cables' absolute costs might be even greater due to the new technologies and installation procedures needed, e.g., dynamic power cables, which include buoyancy components and joints. Furthermore, floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) will likely have higher power ratings than in current offshore projects, resulting in the use of power cables with higher voltage levels. Therefore, optimising the IA topology could mean a considerable reduction in overall costs.

Most of the literature on IA cabling optimisation focuses on bottom-fixed wind farms, while only a limited number of studies examine this topic in the context of FOW [6]. The most basic optimisation method found in the literature is to minimise the total cable length, which directly affects the acquisition costs, power losses, and trenching length, if applicable. However, these optimisations tend to become ineffective when multiple cable types or the farm's overall lifetime (operational expenditures (OPEX) and decommissioning expenditures (DECEX)) is to be considered. In other cases, the minimisation of investment costs and the maximisation of annual energy production (AEP) are combined as the objective function of the model. These two factors can be accounted for by setting the levelised cost of energy (LCOE) as the objective function, considering the entire lifetime of the OWF [6].

The optimisation models applied in the literature can be grouped into deterministic, heuristic, and metaheuristic. Deterministic methods present a global optimum result, but they correspond to large computational times and usually require simplified models. Heuristics and metaheuristics provide the possibility of considering all the complexity of physical modelling, although they do not guarantee an optimal solution [7].

For deterministic approaches, mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) is, in general, computationally efficient and the preferred option. This is used in several papers, such as [8–11]. Chadee et al. [11] propose a planning method for the optimal power collection system while siting and sizing the offshore substations (OSSs) in a large-scale OWF. They achieve a capital expenditures (CAPEX) reduction of 23% and reduce power losses by 44% compared with a conventional design.

Heuristics are problem-dependent algorithms that build solutions through a sequence of steps guided by a stochastic search process. Consequently, they can explore a wider range of possibilities and often yield better results in less time; however, their outputs may be unstable or converge to a local optimum, as they do not exhaustively explore the entire search space. They cannot guarantee an optimal solution but may provide near-optimal solutions while maintaining a relatively low computational cost. Examples of heuristic algorithms are Prim [12,13], Dijkstra, Kurka, Clarke and Wright savings [14–16], or Esau–Williams [10] algorithms.

Metaheuristics are techniques used to lead the search process towards detecting near-optimal solutions across a sufficiently large problem space without requiring excessive computational resources. They are typically applied to refine an initial solution through an iterative improvement process. The two most common metaheuristics found in IA cabling optimisation literature are the genetic algorithm (GA) [17–21], and the particle swarm optimisation (PSO) algorithm [14,22–27], which mimic naturally occurring phenomena.

GAs use principles of evolution to generate and evaluate new solutions. Wang et al. [21] created chromosomes that incorporate wind turbine (WT) interconnections, cable types, and potential OSS locations, ensuring each chromosome represents a complete cabling configuration. They introduce a power loss model that accounts for variable wind speeds when calculating wake losses within a set OWF layout. The objective is to minimise both CAPEX and power loss costs. Their findings indicate that this approach achieves substantial cost reductions compared to the traditional sequential-step method, where the cabling length is minimised first and then cable type is selected.

On the other hand, the PSO algorithm is based on the collective dynamics observed in social animal groups. PSO is used to optimise IA cabling, the OSS position, or both simultaneously. Qi et al. [27] focus its implementation on IA cabling. The authors prescribe the WT connections with a Voronoi diagram and then implement an adaptive PSO with local search to optimise the IA cable configuration. The evaluated function includes the CAPEX associated with the initial cable installation and also accounts for energy losses caused by cable resistances over the operational lifetime of the OWF. The proposed method finds a solution that is 12.74% better than the benchmark.

For FOW application, IA dynamic cables need to be compliant with the floater's motions and hence must adjust their shape without harming the electricity flow or its connection to the floating substructure. There are only three IA optimisation studies considering the unique characteristics of FOW. The first study [28] implemented an adapted PSO model in a FOWF with a fixed layout comprising 50 WTs and one OSS, considering a lazy-wave configuration for the dynamic cables. The objective function encompasses the acquisition cost, cost due to power losses, and cost of expected but not supplied energy (due to failures). The authors were able to optimise the layout, achieving an 8% reduction in power losses and cable length and a 6% decrease in total costs. The second study is [29], which used a two-layer optimisation method. In the hierarchical framework, the upper tier utilises Binary PSO to identify the most efficient connections and cable selection between the WTs and the OSSs, while the lower tier refines WT-to-WT connections through an Improved Monte Carlo Tree Search (IMCTS). The authors demonstrate that the proposed model obtains significant reductions compared to GA, Binary PSO-Sweep-IMCTS and Binary PSO-AA-GA. The last study [30] uses an incremental approach comprising three sequential MILPs followed by a heuristic for solution refinement. The optimisation is applied to pre-existing layouts originally defined for bottom-fixed technology. Model 1 introduces a simple method to consider safety zones by removing connections to avoid mechanical interferences between dynamic cables and mooring lines. Model 2 extends this by including variables to adjust the positions of the mooring lines, and Model 3 increases the degrees of freedom by allowing changes to the touchdown position. With the results of 2 cases, the authors show that the Model 2 achieves a global optimum within seconds using a modern branch-and-cut solver and that wrapping Model 3 in the heuristic allows for an additional cost refinement.

Given the promising performance of PSO algorithms and the limited number of optimisation frameworks specifically adapted to FOW applications, the motivation for this study arises. The LCOE is adopted as the objective function as it provides a comprehensive representation of FOW farm performance. Accordingly, this paper includes all FOWF costs (CAPEX, OPEX and DECEX), as well as the AEP including power flow calculations, ensuring that both expenditures and energy yield are accurately reflected. Particular attention is devoted to the estimation of dynamic cable lengths using lazy wave configuration, a characteristic that distinguishes FOW from bottom-fixed installations and significantly influences IA costs. Furthermore, although the IA cabling problem is inherently discrete, the proposed optimisation framework employs a continuous decision variable encoded

within the PSO formulation. At each iteration, the continuous solution generated by the PSO is discretised to produce a feasible tree cable topology using a clustering procedure combined with minimum spanning trees (MSTs).

The main novelties of this paper are the introduction of a new cable length calculation method based on [31], which enables fast and accurate estimation, and the development of a hybrid continuous–discrete structure, representing a methodological advancement in FOW IA cabling optimisation. The continuous geometric representation enables the algorithm to explore the solution space more effectively, maintain swarm diversity, and mitigate premature convergence, while providing improved scalability and adaptability compared to conventional discrete approaches.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the objective function along with the modelling of each parameter and variable involved. The optimisation model is presented in Section 3 and applied in Section 4, and the study concludes with the findings discussed in Section 5.

2. Floating Offshore Wind Farm Modelling

This section outlines the data and methodology required to obtain the values necessary for calculating the objective function. The objective function represents the value to be minimised by the optimisation model, in this case, the LCOE, which is computed as

$$LCOE = \min \left(\frac{CAPEX + \sum_{y=1}^n \frac{OPEX_y}{(1+r)^y} + \frac{DECEX}{(1+r)^{n+1}}}{AEP \sum_{y=1}^n \frac{1}{(1+r)^y}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where CAPEX is the capital expenditures, which involves the development, manufacturing, transportation, installation (T&I) and commissioning costs; OPEX_y is the operation expenditures of year *y*, which involves the operation and maintenance (O&M) costs; DECEX is the decommissioning expenditures, which involves the decommissioning costs; AEP is the annual energy production; *r* is the discount rate; and *n* is the lifetime of the FOWF in years.

A flowchart (Figure 1) is provided below to illustrate how the parameters and variables described in the following subsections interact within the LCOE calculation.

Figure 1. Flowchart illustrating the relationships between parameters and variables involved in the objective function. Fixed values are shown as rectangles, while variable values are represented by hexagons according to the modelling framework described in this section.

2.1. Parameters

This subsection presents the parameters required to calculate the previously described objective function. These parameters include data on different components and life-cycle stages of the FOWF and are project-specific. Furthermore, the data and their corresponding sources used to represent the case study analysed in this work are provided at the end of this subsection.

2.1.1. Anchors and Mooring Lines

The anchors are characterised by their price per unit, the number of anchors per WT, and the number of WTs in the FOWF. This determines the anchors' procurement cost. To estimate the cost of the mooring lines, the procedure begins with calculating the cost for a single WT based on the description of a station keeping system at a reference depth. This cost is then extrapolated to each WT location by scaling it according to the ratio between the local water depth and the reference depth. This process is therefore characterised by the depths of all WT locations. The costs of these two components are presented in Table 1.

2.1.2. Floating Substructure and Tower

The floating substructure has several attributed costs that need to be considered, including material procurements, manufacturing area leasing, labour and equipment. Additionally, the cable hang-off depth is required for cable length calculations. For the tower, only the procurement costs are required, hence the price per unit. In this case, the tower costs are included in the floating substructure costs, as shown in Table 1.

2.1.3. Wind Turbine

The WT comprises the nacelle and the rotor. The information required is the unit cost, the rotor diameter, the hub height, the rated power, the electrical efficiency, the power curve, and the thrust coefficients. This information is used to compute the costs and the AEP. Table 1 presents the main WT parameters, and Figure 2 displays the power curve, along with the associated thrust coefficient curve.

2.1.4. Inter-Array Cables

The IA cables connect the WTs and transmit the generated energy to the OSS. The parameters to describe its costs and properties are their costs per unit length subject to economies of scale, the costs of the different hardware components, such as buoyancies, joints, tethers, or stiffeners, and the cable properties, which are the power capacity, the resistivity, the nominal voltage, the conductor section, the inductance, and the capacitance. In this case, the IA cable properties are confidential and therefore cannot be disclosed.

2.1.5. Offshore Substation

There are different types of substations, and their selection depends on the transmission technology selected and the requirements of the specific projects. The most commonly used OSS type is equipped with transformers in order to increase the medium/high voltage from the collection system to high/very high voltage, thus helping to decrease the power losses in the export cable. In other cases, the OSS converts alternating current into direct current; hence, it requires a converter instead of a transformer [32]. For example, for an offshore transformer substation, its price and quantity are necessary to determine the OSS costs, and the transformer reactance and the reactive compensation, if any, are required for the electrical performance. The OSS costs are presented in Table 1.

2.1.6. Export Cable

The export cable is defined by its price per unit length and by a set of properties influencing its power losses, including capacity, insulation, armour and sheath thickness, inductance, capacitance, and section. As for IA cables, the export cable properties are confidential and cannot be disclosed.

2.1.7. Life-Cycle Stages

The costs related to the development, T&I, commissioning, O&M, and decommissioning processes are expressed as fixed values per MW of installed capacity. This is because they are considered independent of the IA cabling, as the number of cables does not change through the optimisation algorithm and the impact of the cable lengths variations on these costs is negligible. The development, T&I, and commissioning costs are included in the CAPEX, while O&M costs are accounted for in the OPEX. Decommissioning costs are considered within the DECEX. Availability is modelled as a fixed value. It depends on maintenance, failure probabilities, operational procedures, and weather conditions, and it is considered as a factor in the AEP calculation. Each of these values are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

2.1.8. Project-Specific Information

This section presents the project-specific information required to evaluate the objective function defined in Equation (1). The data compiled here characterise the FOWF considered in the study, encompassing its main components, life-cycle stages, and relevant technical and economic parameters explained in the previous sections. For clarity, the information is organised into different tables: Table 1 summarises the main parameters associated with the different components; Figure 2 displays the power and thrust coefficient curves of the WT, specifically the Vestas V164-8.0MW model (Vestas Wind Systems A/S, Aarhus, Denmark) employed in this work; Table 2 outlines the life-cycle costs, and finally, Table 3 presents the project settings, including the assumed lifetime, availability and discount rate.

Table 1. Component parameters.

Parameter	Value	Source
Anchors costs ** (M EUR/GU *)	0.69	[33]
Mooring lines costs ** (M EUR/GU *)	0.55	[33]
Floating substructure and Tower costs ** (M EUR/GU *)	4.88	[34]
Offshore substation costs ** (M EUR/MW)	0.36	[35]
Wind turbine costs ** (M EUR)	10	[36]
Wind turbine rated power (MW)	8	[37]
Electrical efficiency (%)	99.5	[37]
Rotor diameter (m)	164	[37]
Hub height (m)	110	[37]

* GU: Generation Unit. ** A contingency allowance of 5% is to be applied to these values.

Table 2. Life-cycle stages costs (excluding manufacturing).

Life-Cycle	Value	Source
Development (% of CAPEX)	5.7	[34]
T&I and commissioning (k EUR/MW)	1000	[34]
Operation (k EUR/MW/year)	28	[34]
Maintenance (k EUR/MW/year)	62.5	[34]
Decommissioning (k EUR/MW)	625	[34]

Figure 2. Power and thrust coefficient curves of the Vestas V164-8.0MW WT model adapted from [37].

Table 3. Project settings.

Parameter	Value	Source
Lifetime (years)	25	[38]
Availability (%)	96	[39]
Discount rate (%)	8	[38]

2.2. Variables

In this subsection, the elements that vary during the optimisation and the methodology to compute them are described in detail. These include the length of the IA cables and the resulting power losses described within the AEP calculation.

2.2.1. Length of the Inter-Array Cables

The required cable length $L_{t,ij}$ for each possible connection between nodes i and j (including WT and OSS) are computed considering the selected dynamic cable form. Here, the lazy wave is assumed, which can be described via following equations:

$$D_{v,i} = H_{depth,i} - H_{hod} \quad (2)$$

$$L_{d,i} = D_{v,i} \left(\frac{0.99 \cdot D_{v,i} + 128.44}{D_{v,i} + 9.87} \right); \quad (3)$$

$$D_{h,i} = \frac{0.02 \cdot D_{v,i}^2 + 236.21 \cdot D_{v,i} + 4634.80}{D_{v,i} + 103.00}; \quad (4)$$

$$L_{s,ij} = 1.05 \cdot D_{E,ij} - (D_{h,i} + D_{h,j}); \text{ and} \quad (5)$$

$$L_{t,ij} = L_{s,ij} + L_{d,i} + L_{d,j} \quad (6)$$

where $D_{v,i}$ is the vertical distance between the hang-off point and the seabed, determined by the $H_{depth,i}$, which is the water depth in the WT i location and the H_{hod} , which is the hang-off depth. $L_{d,i}$ is the dynamic cable length in WT i , $D_{h,i}$ is the horizontal distance between the floating substructure, and the touchdown point on the seabed at WT i , $D_{E,ij}$ is the Euclidean distance between WT i and WT j , $L_{s,ij}$ is the static cable length between WTs i and j , and $L_{t,ij}$ is the total cable length to connect WT i and j . The 5% increase in the static

part of the cable in Equation (5) allows for routing around the mooring system anchors, as stipulated in [28]. These equations are achieved by the regression of the cable length calculation performed in [31] applied to multiple water depths.

2.2.2. Annual Energy Production

The first step is calculating the mechanical power, for which the average power losses due to wakes are necessary. In large OWFs, wake losses account for approximately 10% to 20% of the total output power [40]; therefore, they play a relevant role in calculating the LCOE. Several wake models exist to estimate these losses with their respective accuracies and complexities. However, the implemented wake model is based on the Jensen [41] and Katic [42] models, since a simple wake model can estimate the losses within an acceptable computational time and accuracy. However, in Jensen's model [41], a wake decay coefficient of 0.1 is used, but further research and experience indicate that for offshore applications, a lower value of 0.04 is recommended [43]. The thrust coefficients are employed to characterise the wind speed deficits in the wake, as described in [42].

This model results in an $m \times p \times n$ matrix containing wind speed values, where m is the number of wind speeds, p is the number of direction bins, and n is the number of WTs. To improve model accuracy, interval speed deficits are averaged by varying the wind direction in 0.9° steps between the upper and lower bounds of each direction interval. The resulting wind velocities determine the mechanical power output of each WT along its power curve (Figure 2), and by applying the WT efficiency, the corresponding electrical power is obtained.

Next, a power flow using the Newton-Raphson method is conducted for each power generation. It provides the total output electric power for each case (n wind velocities and p directions). Subsequently, the dielectric losses are computed for each resultant connection k as

$$D_{loss,k} = U^2 \cdot 2\pi f \cdot C \cdot \tan\delta, \quad (7)$$

where U is the voltage of the cable; f is the frequency; C is the capacitance of the cable, which varies with its cable length; and $\tan\delta$ is the dielectric loss tangent of the insulating material. The sum of the losses across the connections represents the total dielectric losses. By accounting for these losses in the total output electric power, the power transmitted by the onshore substation (ONS) is determined for each wind condition. Finally, the availability is applied to obtain the AEP. As the probabilities of each wind speed and wind direction are given by the wind data at the site, the energy can therefore be computed as

$$AEP = \sum_{v=v_{min}}^{v_{max}} \sum_{a=0}^{360} P_{trans,v,a} \cdot p_v \cdot p_a \cdot T \cdot A, \quad (8)$$

where v_{min} is the cut-in wind speed of the WT and v_{max} is the cut-out wind speed, $P_{trans,v,a}$ is the power transmitted by the ONS with a specific wind speed v and wind direction a , p_v is the probability of the wind speed, p_a is the probability of the wind direction, T is the hours per year, given as 8766, and A is the availability, which equals a fixed value.

3. Optimisation Model

In this section, the specifications of the optimisation model are described. Specifically, Section 3.1 outlines the adaptive PSO and Section 3.2 explains how the model is implemented.

3.1. Adaptive Particle Swarm Optimisation

The PSO is a population-based metaheuristic optimisation algorithm that, although it does not guarantee the global optimal solution, generally exhibits good performance with a considerably low computational burden compared to several alternative methods [44,45] and requires relatively little effort in parameter tuning [46], making it a simple yet effective approach for IA cabling optimisation problems.

The initialisation of the method requires a vector of the initial positions of the particles set as $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i)$, where i refers to the number of particles. Each particle corresponds to a potential solution of the optimisation problem and therefore provides a different result for the objective function. The optimisation process is guided by $Pbest_i^k$ and $Gbest^k$, which represent the best position found so far by the particle i up to iteration k , and the best position found so far among all particles up to that iteration, respectively. Therefore, in the first iteration, $Pbest_i^1$ corresponds to the initial solution of particle i , while $Gbest^1$ mirrors the best initial position found by all particles.

The velocity v_i^{k+1} , which determines the movement within the search space of the particle i at iteration $k + 1$, is calculated as follows:

$$v_i^{k+1} = w^k \cdot v_i^k + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (Pbest_i^k - x_i^k) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (Gbest^k - x_i^k), \quad (9)$$

where w^k is the inertia weight in iteration k , v_i^k is the previous velocity of the particle i , c_1 is the cognitive acceleration coefficient, c_2 is the social acceleration coefficient, and r_1 and r_2 are random numbers between 0 and 1 [47].

The adaptive behaviour of the employed PSO is achieved through the changing inertia weight, which linearly decreases each iteration. This practice has been shown in several studies (e.g., [48,49]) to enhance solution quality and convergence speed of conventional PSO when solving multimodal or high-dimensional problems, since the inertia weight progressively shift the algorithm's focus from global exploration to local exploitation as the optimisation process advances. Accordingly, an adaptive PSO with linear decreasing inertia weight is applied, where the inertia weight is updated as

$$w^k = w_{max} - \left(\frac{w_{max} - w_{min}}{k_{max}} \right) k, \quad (10)$$

where w_{max} and w_{min} are the set maximum and minimum inertia weight, and k_{max} is the maximum number of iterations. If the stopping criterion is defined as a computational time limit, k corresponds to the advanced time and k_{max} to the set maximum time limit [47], both in seconds.

The position of the x_i^{k+1} changes in each iteration depending on the achieved velocities v_i^{k+1} as

$$x_i^{k+1} = x_i^k + v_i^{k+1}. \quad (11)$$

After each iteration, the objective function is calculated for each of the resulting particles, and $Pbest_i^k$ and $Gbest^k$ are updated, if necessary.

This process of updating the particles' positions, velocities, personal bests, and global best is repeated until the user-defined stopping criterion is met. Such a criterion may correspond to convergence, a maximum number of iterations, or a predefined computational time limit.

For the purpose of this optimisation, different PSO parameter configurations have been tested to evaluate their influence on the algorithm's performance. The analysis revealed that the parameter set shown in Table 4 provides good and consistent performance, making it a suitable choice for the optimisation problem considered.

Table 4. PSO parameters.

Parameter	Value
Particles	50
Minimum inertia weight	0.2
Maximum inertia weight	0.9
Cognitive acceleration coefficient	2
Social acceleration coefficient	2
Iterations	500

3.2. Implementation

The first step is defining an initial solution to reduce the computational time of the PSO by guiding the search within a promising space. This solution represents the connections between WTs and OSSs obtained from the MST of WT groups. The groups are formed by clustering WTs by their angle relative to the OSS and by limiting the number of WTs per group to keep within the cable ampacity. The MST is defined as a weighted spanning tree with the minimum possible weight among all possible spanning trees [50]. In this case, the vertices are taken as the WTs and OSSs, the edges represent the IA cables, and the weights mirror to the cable lengths. Therefore, the initial solution corresponds to the IA cabling with the lowest cable length per cluster. The clustering process will be further explained when describing the PSO execution in this subsection.

The PSO-based optimisation model is implemented using the MATLAB (R2022b) programming language and has been adapted in order to solve the IA cabling optimisation. The variable decisions in this model are continuous and correspond to a theoretical angle rotation of the WTs related to the OSS. Therefore, a particle contains as many angles as WTs are in the FOWF. These angles rotate the WTs and give a momentary layout in order to provide a unique clustering for each of the particles. A sweep algorithm is applied to this layout. The sweep line starts at the largest angle gap without WTs in the FOWF, and groups the WTs into clusters, ensuring a uniform distribution within each cluster as it progresses clockwise. Subsequently, the connection between WTs is established with MSTs, with the closest WT to the OSS of each branch as the feeder WT (i.e., the WT directly connected to the OSS). The rotation angles are only applied to establish the temporary layout used for clustering and connecting the WTs of the specific particle solution. It is important to note that it has no effect on the actual layout used for the calculation of the cable lengths and the objective function. This procedure effectively discretises the continuous variables into the required connections between WTs, completing the hybrid structure of the optimisation approach.

The swarm population is set to 50 particles, and the initial population is randomly generated with values between -7° and 7° , which represent the rotation angles of the WTs relative to the OSS, which is considered the origin of coordinate system. Therefore, the initial population gives 50 potential solutions, each specifying the rotation angles of all WTs.

For a given case of 63 WTs, the clustering is set as seen in Figure 3. In this case, the maximum number of WTs per cluster is nine, and the clustering is applied without any rotation angle, meaning that no changes to the farm layout are carried out, which would otherwise result in WTs being part of other clusters. Therefore, finding the MST for each of these branches correspond to the initial solution of this optimisation case.

The process becomes clearer with the explanation of this example. The index of each WT is assigned according to their geographic coordinates, beginning with the westernmost WT at the highest latitude and continuing sequentially southward and then eastward. The clustering process starts at WT 56, as it corresponds to the first WT positioned clockwise

from the largest gap between WTs in the FOWF (Figure 3a). This first cluster ends with WT 37 and involves WTs 56, 50, 38, 44, 49, 55, 60, 32 and finally 37. The subsequent cluster is closed by the WT 10. Because there is more than one WT with the same angle, the order of selection is from the smallest index number to the largest. Therefore, the cluster consists of WTs 21, 43, 26, 15, 31, 48, 5, 20 and 10 (Figure 3b). The cluster creation follows this process until all WTs are assigned (Figure 3c). The next step is to identify the feeder WTs for each cluster. In this case, WTs 60, 48, 54, 35, 47, 59, and 63 are chosen, which correspond to the closest WT to the OSS per cluster.

Figure 3. Clustering process. (a) Finding the largest gap between WTs, (b) clockwise cluster partitioning, and (c) final grouping of clusters. Blue and red markers illustrate which WTs have been clustered and their corresponding cluster assignment.

This process is repeated for each particle generated by the algorithm. Once the connections of the different WT clusters are defined, the following constraints must be satisfied:

- Cluster sizes are limited to the ampacity of one IA cable.
- No loops are allowed.
- The number of clusters is limited to the number of allowed feeder cables of the OSS.
- Cable crossings are not allowed as it influences the performance of the IA, as well as installation and maintenance processes.

The first three constraints are inherently met by the algorithm, whereas the fourth constraint requires verification. In case the constraint is not satisfied, the possible solution is discarded. If the constraint is met, the LCOE is calculated. Then, P_{best} and G_{best} are checked and modified in case a new solution provides a lower LCOE than the current values and the particle's positions are updated for the next iteration. This process is conducted until the set maximum number of iterations or time limit is reached.

Final adjustments are applied to assess whether small modifications can result in lower LCOEs. Adjustment 1 tests a "skip-a-node" rewiring to reduce the LCOE. For every inter-WT cable (excluding those that export power directly to the OSS), we retarget the cable to the next WT in the chain. For example, if $WT3 \rightarrow WT2$ and $WT2 \rightarrow WT1$ (connections (3,2) and (2,1)),

we replace (3,2) with a direct link $WT3 \rightarrow WT1$, yielding (3,1) and (2,1). This is evaluated for each connection, and the layout is updated whenever it lowers the LCOE. Adjustment 2 targets junctions where a WT receives two inbound cables. Suppose $WT3 \rightarrow WT2$ and $WT4 \rightarrow WT2$, with $WT2 \rightarrow WT1$ (i.e., (3,2), (4,2), (2,1)). The adjustment tests re-rooting the local hub so the aggregator shifts from $WT2$ to either $WT3$ or $WT4$ while preserving delivery to $WT1$: if $WT4$ becomes the aggregator, the connections become (3,4), (2,4), and (4,1); if $WT3$ becomes the aggregator, they become (4,3), (2,3), and (3,1). In both cases, the new aggregator forwards its own generation plus the combined power from the other two WTs to $WT1$. The layout is adopted only if it reduces LCOE. These checked adjustments are shown in Figure 4. After this step, the resulting connection is the final solution of the optimisation.

The process is depicted in form of a flowchart, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Simplified examples of improved connections with (a) adjustment 1 and (b) adjustment 2.

Figure 5. Model optimisation flowchart.

4. Case Study

In this section, the optimisation model is applied to two FOWFs, both located at the same site off the coast of Porto, Portugal. The studied cases include a medium-sized FOWF

and a large FOWF. The improvement achieved with the optimisation model is shown by the variations of LCOE, cable acquisition costs, AEP, and cable length compared to the initial solution. Furthermore, the reduction in emissions is expressed as the IA cabling manufacturing carbon intensity.

4.1. Case Definition

The wind resource is provided by the Global Wind Atlas [51] and is represented by the wind rose in Figure 6. The local bathymetry is also required, and a layer from the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO) [52] is introduced to the program. The water depths are interpolated for each WT and OSS positions, which results in depths between 110 and 150 m.

Figure 6. Wind rose (at 100 m height).

4.2. Medium FOWF

The medium-sized FOWF comprises 63 WTs, resulting in a total power capacity of 504 MW. It has been optimised five times, producing the LCOE evolutions across the iterations shown in Figure 7, with the maximum number of iterations set to 500. In runs 1, 3, 4, and 5, the result is the same. However, in all four cases, the final result is achieved after applying the adjustments. The improvement by the adjustments is reflected by the vertical line at iteration 500. Meanwhile, run 2 shows just a little improvement from the adjustments and results in a higher LCOE. This shows a degree of robustness, as the algorithm found the same optimal solution in four out of five runs. The 500 iterations are run in about 2 h using an Intel Core i5 with 1.3 GHz, 16 GB of RAM, and Windows 11 Pro operating system. Other stopping criteria have been checked, such as the maximum computational time at 6 h, but no better solution has been found.

The resulting optimal connection is shown in Figure 8, which visualises both the initial solution represented by dashed orange lines, found by applying only the clusters and the MST algorithm, and the final solution in solid black lines. It should be noted that many connections are shared. Hence, the initial solution already provides a good estimation of the optimal IA connection. Table 5 compares key performance indicators of the initial and final solution, underlining the initial solution's quality. The relative reduction in the values compared to the initial solution is small. It is observed that the reduction in LCOE is

0.018%, which equals a decrease of 0.022 EUR/MWh; the reduction in cable acquisition costs is 0.18%, corresponding to a decrease of 283,059 EUR, and the AEP has increased by 0.057%, amounting to an additional 1115 MWh annually and 27.9 GWh during its lifetime. Furthermore, the cable length has been reduced by 640 m, representing a reduction of 0.608%.

Figure 7. LCOE evolution for 5 different runs.

In addition to reducing the LCOE, the cabling optimisation directly effects the carbon footprint of the IA cable manufacturing, as shorter lengths translate into lower emissions. Moreover, if a higher AEP is achieved on the optimised solution compared to the initial solution, it further reduces the carbon intensity. Consequently, a comparison of the carbon intensity associated with the embodied emissions of the IA cable between the initial and optimised solution is presented. Based on global warming potential factors from EcoInvent and GaBi databases and the specific mass per meter of cable, the IA cable emissions per meter are determined to be 85.6 kgCO_{2eq}/m. Multiplying this factor by the cable length, the manufacturing carbon footprint is obtained. Dividing these emissions by the total lifetime energy production of the FOWF yields the carbon intensity attributable to the embodied emissions of the IA cable. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Comparison between initial solution and optimised solution of the medium FOWF.

Property	Initial Solution	Optimised Solution	Difference	Difference (%)
LCOE (EUR/MWh)	121.8097	121.7875	−0.022	−0.018
IA cable acquisition costs (EUR)	157,469,500	157,186,441	−283,059	−0.180
AEP (MWh)	1,946,558	1,947,673	1115	0.057
IA cable length (m)	106,146	105,506	−640	−0.608
IA cabling manufacturing carbon intensity (kgCO _{2eq} /MWh)	0.187	0.186	−0.001	−0.660

Figure 8. Optimal connection obtained for the medium FOWF.

4.3. Large FOWF

The large FOWF has 130 WTs, summing to a total power capacity of 1040 MW. As discussed above, the site conditions are the same as in the medium FOWF case, and the only changes in the inputs are the locations of the WTs and the OSS. In this case, the 500 iterations are reached in approximately 6 h as more connections transform into higher computational times. Several runs achieved very similar results, resulting in the LCOEs shown in Table 6.

Table 6. LCOE results of the initial solution and 5 different runs for the large FOWF.

Case	LCOE (EUR/MWh)
Initial solution	119.7313
Run 1	119.6144
Run 2	119.6152
Run 3	119.6169
Run 4	119.6157
Run 5	119.6109

As observed, only the third decimal varies between iterations. The latter solution, which achieves the minimum LCOE between the five runs, is the one shown in Figure 9 and

Table 7. The difference in LCOE from the initial solution is 0.12 EUR/MWh, corresponding to a decrease of 0.101%. Acquisition costs are reduced by approximately EUR 4 M, and carbon intensity decreases by 0.007 kgCO_{2eq}/MWh. Finally, the AEP increases by 630 MWh (a relative increase of 0.016%), reaching a total of 15.75 GWh over its lifetime.

The relative LCOE reduction achieved for the large FOWF is six times larger than that obtained by the medium-sized FOWF optimisation (see Section 4.2). Similarly, the IA cabling acquisition costs and manufacturing carbon intensity exhibit larger relative decreases, 1.461% versus 0.180 % and 3.644% versus 0.660%, respectively. The only key performance indicator that has not improved relative to the medium case is the AEP. Overall, the reductions achieved by the large FOWF are greater than those for the 63 WT case, indicating that the initial solution provides worse results for larger FOWFs.

Figure 9. (a) Optimal connections obtained for the large FOWF and (b) performance of the LCOE and inertia weight during the optimisation process.

Table 7. Comparison between initial solution and optimised solution of the large FOWF.

Property	Initial Solution	Optimised Solution	Difference	Difference (%)
LCOE (EUR/MWh)	119.7313	119.6109	−0.120	−0.101
IA cable acquisition costs (EUR)	262,205,200	258,375,672	−3,829,528	−1.461
AEP (MWh)	3,934,012	3,934,642	630	0.016
IA cable length (m)	211,100	203,441	−7659	−3.628
IA cabling manufacturing carbon intensity (kgCO _{2eq} /MWh)	0.184	0.177	−0.007	−3.644

5. Conclusions

In this paper, an optimisation model based on a PSO algorithm adapted for FOWF IA cabling is presented. The model applies a wake model considering stochastic wind velocities and directions for an accurate computation of the mechanical power, and models power flow and dielectric losses for the power loss calculation. Furthermore, the specific cable length of the dynamic cable configuration and its acquisition costs are considered. The local dynamic cable length are accurately calculated by the developed model in this study, which enables rapid calculation. The optimisation model is applied to a medium and a large FOWF, and the results are compared with those from the initial clustering- and MST-based solution. The algorithm yields layouts that satisfy all constraints while minimising LCOE, with particularly strong improvements for the large FOWF.

The PSO algorithm reduces the LCOE of the medium FOWF with 63 WTs by 0.018%, corresponding to a decrease in acquisition costs of EUR 283,059 and an increase in AEP of 1115 MWh. Repeated runs show that these optimal results are robust and can be obtained with an execution time of about 2 h.

For the large FOWF, with 130 WTs and 1,040 MW, the differences are larger for all metrics except AEP. The reduction in LCOE is 0.1%, almost six times that of the medium FOWF, and cable acquisition costs decrease by EUR 3,829,528. This indicates that the algorithm achieves greater cost reductions for larger FOWFs. However, in this case, the LCOE varies between runs, showing that the algorithm can converge to different near-optimal solutions.

Alongside cost reductions, the algorithm achieves a decrease in global warming potential, with the IA cabling manufacturing carbon intensity decreasing by 0.660% and 3.644% for the medium and large cases, respectively.

In conclusion, the algorithm yields minor relative reductions in LCOE, indicating the strong performance of the initial solution. Consequently, the initial solution is well-suited for conceptual design, as it also enables faster analyses. However, the proposed PSO algorithm outperforms the initial clustering and MST-based approach. Therefore, at the front-end engineering design stage and onwards, the developed algorithm offers a promising tool for refining network layouts and supporting more informed engineering decisions, as it demonstrably enables cost saving on the order of a million euros.

Further work may incorporate cable type selection, as the present study employs a single cable model for all connections between WTs, or a more accurate estimation of the cable length to avoid other subsea elements, such as moorings or seabed obstacles within the FOWF area.

Author Contributions: Conceptualisation, S.V.L. and J.I.R.; methodology, S.V.L. and J.I.R.; writing—original draft preparation, S.V.L.; writing—review and editing, M.D.K., J.I.R. and J.L.D.-G. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work has received financial support from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, subsidised by CDTI through the TRANSMISIONES 2023 program under the OPTIMAR project with grant agreement PLEC2023-010352.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding authors.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

Acronyms

AEP	Annual Energy Production
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
DECEX	Decommissioning Expenditures
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWF	Floating Offshore Wind Farm
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
GA	Genetic Algorithm
IA	Inter-Array
IMCTS	Improved Monte Carlo Tree Search
LCOE	Levelised Cost of Energy
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
MST	Minimum Spanning Tree
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
ONS	Onshore Substation
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
OSS	Offshore Substation
OWF	Offshore Wind Farm
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimisation
T&I	Transportation and Installation
WT	Wind Turbine

Symbols

n	Lifetime
r	Discount rate
$D_{v,i}$	Vertical distance between the hang-off point and the seabed in WT i [m]
$H_{depth,i}$	Water depth in WT i [m]
H_{hod}	Hang-off depth [m]
$L_{d,i}$	Dynamic cable length in WT i [m]
$D_{h,i}$	Horizontal distance between the floating substructure and touchdown point at WT i [m]
$L_{s,ij}$	Static cable length between WT i and WT j [m]
$D_{E,i}$	Euclidean distance between WT i and WT j [m]
$L_{t,ij}$	Total cable length between WT i and WT j [m]
$D_{loss,k}$	Dielectric losses of connection k [MW]
U	Voltage of the cable [kV]
f	Frequency [Hz]
C	Capacitance of the cable k [F]
$\tan\delta$	Dielectric loss tangent of the insulating material
v_{min}, v_{max}	Cut-in and cut-out wind speeds of the WT [m/s]
$P_{trans,v,a}$	Power transmitted by the ONS with a specific wind speed v and wind direction a [MW]
p_v	Probability of the wind speed v
p_a	Probability of the wind direction a
T	Hours per year
A	Availability
v_i^k	Velocity of particle i at iteration k
w^k	Inertia weight in iteration k
c_1, c_2	Acceleration coefficients
r_1, r_2	Random values between 0 and 1
$Pbest_i^k$	Optimal position of particle i up to iteration k
x_i^k	Position of particle i at iteration k
$Gbest^k$	Optimal position found by all particles up to iteration k

w_{min}, w_{max}	Set minimum and maximum inertia weight
k_{max}	Set maximum number of iterations

References

- Bouckaert, S.; Pales, A.F.; McGlade, C.; Remme, U.; Wanner, B.; Varro, L.; D'Ambrosio, D.; Spencer, T. *Net Zero by 2050: A Roadmap for the Global Energy Sector*; Technical Report; IEA: Paris, France, 2021.
- Europe, W. Wind Delivers the Energy Society Wants. Available online: <https://windeurope.org/about-wind/wind-energy-today/> (accessed on 25 September 2023).
- McCoy, A.; Musial, W.; Hammond, R.; Hernando, D.M.; Duffy, P.; Beiter, P.; Pérez, P.; Baranowski, R.; Reber, G.; Spitsen, P. *Offshore Wind Market Report: 2024 Edition*; Technical Report; NREL: Golden, CO, USA, 2024.
- Hutchinson, M.; Zhao, F.; Backwell, B.; Clarke, E.; Esther Fang, R.F.; Gitobu, J.; Khinda, N.; Ladwa, R.; Lathigara, A.; Liang, W.; et al. *Global Wind Report 2023*; Technical Report; GWEC: Brussels, Belgium, 2024.
- Hou, P.; Zhu, J.; Ma, K.; Yang, G.; Hu, W.; Chen, Z. A review of offshore wind farm layout optimization and electrical system design methods. *J. Mod. Power Syst. Clean Energy* **2019**, *7*, 975–986. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Kallinger, M.D.; Rapha, J.I.; Trubat Casal, P.; Domínguez-García, J.L. Offshore Electrical Grid Layout Optimization for Floating Wind—A Review. *Clean Technol.* **2023**, *5*, 791–827. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Pérez-Rúa, J.A.; Cutululis, N. Electrical Cable Optimization in Offshore Wind Farms—A review. *IEEE Access* **2019**, *7*, 85796–85811. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Dutta, S.; Overbye, T.J. Optimal Wind Farm Collector System Topology Design Considering Total Trenching Length. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* **2012**, *3*, 339–348. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Cerveira, A.; Pires, E.J.S.; Baptista, J. Wind Farm Cable Connection Layout Optimization with Several Substations. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 3615. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Pérez-Rúa, J.A.; Stolpe, M.; Das, K.; Cutululis, N. Global Optimization of Offshore Wind Farm Collection Systems. *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* **2020**, *35*, 2256–2267. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Chadee, X.T.; Clarke, R.M. Large-scale wind energy potential of the Caribbean region using near-surface reanalysis data. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2014**, *30*, 45–58. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Serrano González, J.; Trigo García, A.L.; Burgos Payán, M.; Riquelme Santos, J.; González Rodríguez, A.G. Optimal wind-turbine micro-siting of offshore wind farms: A grid-like layout approach. *Appl. Energy* **2017**, *200*, 28–38. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Zuo, T.; Meng, K.; Tong, Z.; Tang, Y.; Dong, Z.H. Offshore wind farm collector system layout optimization based on self-tracking minimum spanning tree. *Int. Trans. Electr. Energy Syst.* **2019**, *29*, e2729. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Gong, X.; Kuenzel, S.; Pal, B.C. Optimal Wind Farm Cabling. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* **2018**, *9*, 1126–1136. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Zuo, T.; Zhang, Y.; Meng, K.; Dong, Z.Y. Collector System Topology for Large-Scale Offshore Wind Farms Considering Cross-Substation Incorporation. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* **2020**, *11*, 1601–1611. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Zuo, T.; Zhang, Y.; Meng, K.; Tong, Z.; Dong, Z.Y.; Fu, Y. Collector System Topology Design for Offshore Wind Farm's Repowering and Expansion. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* **2021**, *12*, 847–859. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Wade, B.; Pereira, R.; Wade, C. Investigation of offshore wind farm layouts regarding wake effects and cable topology. *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **2019**, *1222*, 012007. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Shin, J.S.; Kim, J.O. Optimal Design for Offshore Wind Farm considering Inner Grid Layout and Offshore Substation Location. *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.* **2017**, *32*, 2041–2048. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Zuo, T.; Zhang, Y.; Meng, K.; Tong, Z.; Dong, Z.Y.; Fu, Y. A Two-Layer Hybrid Optimization Approach for Large-Scale Offshore Wind Farm Collector System Planning. *IEEE Trans. Ind. Inform.* **2021**, *17*, 7433–7444. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Wei, S.; Zhang, L.; Xu, Y.; Fu, Y.; Li, F. Hierarchical Optimization for the Double-Sided Ring Structure of the Collector System Planning of Large Offshore Wind Farms. *IEEE Trans. Sustain. Energy* **2016**, *8*, 1029–1039. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Wang, L.; Wu, J.; Tang, Z.; Wang, T. An Integration Optimization Method for Power Collection Systems of Offshore Wind Farms. *Energies* **2019**, *12*, 3965. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- El Mokhi, C.; Addaim, A. Optimization of Wind Turbine Interconnections in an Offshore Wind Farm Using Metaheuristic Algorithms. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 5761. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Jin, R.; Hou, P.; Yang, G.; Qi, Y.; Chen, C.; Chen, Z. Cable routing optimization for offshore wind power plants via wind scenarios considering power loss cost model. *Appl. Energy* **2019**, *254*, 113719. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Hou, P.; Yang, G.; Hu, W.; Chen, C.; Soltani, M.; Chen, Z. Cable Connection Scheme Optimization for Offshore Wind Farm Considering Wake Effect. In Proceedings of the 2018 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 8–13 July 2018; pp. 1–8. [\[CrossRef\]](#)

25. Hou, P.; Hu, W.; Soltani, M.; Chen, C.; Chen, Z. Combined optimization for offshore wind turbine micro siting. *Appl. Energy* **2017**, *189*, 271–282. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Tao, S.; Xu, Q.; Feijóo, A.; Zheng, G. Joint Optimization of Wind Turbine Micrositing and Cabling in an Offshore Wind Farm. *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid* **2021**, *12*, 834–844. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Qi, Y.; Hou, P.; Liu, G.; Jin, R.; Yang, Z.; Yang, G.; Dong, Z. Cable Connection Optimization for Heterogeneous Offshore Wind Farms via a Voronoi Diagram Based Adaptive Particle Swarm Optimization with Local Search. *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 644. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Lerch, M.; De-Prada-Gil, M.; Molins, C. A metaheuristic optimization model for the inter-array layout planning of floating offshore wind farms. *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* **2021**, *131*, 107128. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Song, D.; Yan, J.; Gao, Y.; Wang, L.; Du, X.; Xu, Z.; Zhang, Z.; Yang, J.; Dong, M.; Chen, Y. Optimization of floating wind farm power collection system using a novel two-layer hybrid method. *Appl. Energy* **2023**, *348*, 121546. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Pérez-Rúa, J.A.; Lund, R.S.; Verelst, D.R.; Abrahamsen, A.B.; Dykes, K. Exact optimization of inter-array dynamic cable networks for Floating Offshore Wind Farms. *Renew. Energy* **2024**, *237*, 121647. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Li, S.; Nguyen, C. Dynamic response of deepwater lazy-wave catenary riser. *Deep. Offshore Technol. Int.* **2010**, *147*, 1–21.
32. Anaya-Lara, O. 12—Offshore wind farm arrays. In *Offshore Wind Farms*; Ng, C., Ran, L., Eds.; Woodhead Publishing: Sawston, UK, 2016; pp. 389–417. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Schwarzkopf, M.A.; Ferreira, V.J.F.; Rapha, J.I.; Catillo, F.; Garcia, R.G. *D6.4 LCOE, CAPEX and OPEX Reduction: Key Performance Indicators and Executive Summary*; COREWIND D6.4; RAMBOLL: Copenhagen, Denmark, 2023.
34. Benveniste, G.; Lerch, M.; de Prada, M.; Kretschmer, M.; Berqué, J.; López, A.; Pérez, G. *Deliverable 2.2. LCOE Tool Description, Technical and Environmental Impact Evaluation Procedure*; LIFES50+ D2.2; Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE), University of Stuttgart: Stuttgart, Germany, 2016.
35. Shelley, S.; Boo, S.; Kim, D.; Luyties, W. Concept Design of Floating Substation for a 200 MW Wind Farm for the Northeast U.S. In Proceedings of the Offshore Technology Conference, Houston, TX, USA, 4–7 May 2020. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. BVG Associates. Guide to a Floating Offshore Wind Farm. 2025. Available online: <https://guidetofloatingoffshorewind.com/> (accessed on 25 September 2023).
37. Vestas Wind Systems A/S. V164-8.0 MW. Brochure via ArchiExpo. Available online: <https://pdf.archiexpo.com/pdf/vestas/vestas-v164-80-mw/88087-134417.html> (accessed on 8 September 2025).
38. Lerch, M.; Borisade, F.; Bhat, J. *Deliverable 2.8 Expected LCOE for Floating Wind Turbines 10 MW+ for 50 m+ Water Depth*; LIFES50+ D2.8; Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE), University of Stuttgart: Stuttgart, Germany, 2016.
39. Schwarzkopf, M.A.; Borisade, F.; Espelage, J.; Johnston, E.; Vicente, R.D.; Muñoz, S.; Hylland, P.; He, W.; Urbano, J.; Comas, F.J.; et al. *D4.2 Floating Wind O&M Strategies Assessment*; COREWIND D4.2; RAMBOLL: Copenhagen, Denmark, 2023.
40. Barthelmie, R.J.; Hansen, K.; Frandsen, S.T.; Rathmann, O.; Schepers, J.; Schlez, W.; Phillips, J.; Rados, K.; Zervos, A.; Politis, E.; et al. Modelling and measuring flow and wind turbine wakes in large wind farms offshore. *Wind. Energy Int. J. Prog. Appl. Wind. Power Convers. Technol.* **2009**, *12*, 431–444. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Jensen, N. *A Note on Wind Generator Interaction*; Number 2411 in Risø-M; Risø National Laboratory: Roskilde, Denmark, 1983.
42. Katic, I.; Højstrup, J.; Jensen, N.O. A simple model for cluster efficiency. In Proceedings of the European wind energy association conference and exhibition. A. Raguzzi, Rome, Italy, 7–9 October 1987; pp. 407–410.
43. DTU. WASP. Available online: https://wasp.dtu.dk/software/wasp#details__wakeeffectmodel (accessed on 2 July 2024).
44. Eberhart, R.; Kennedy, J. A new optimizer using particle swarm theory. In Proceedings of the MHS'95, Proceedings of the Sixth International Symposium on Micro Machine and Human Science, Nagoya, Japan, 4–6 October 1995; pp. 39–43. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Souza Lima, C.A.; Lapa, C.M.F.; do N.A. Pereira, C.M.; da Cunha, J.J.; Alvim, A.C.M. Comparison of computational performance of GA and PSO optimization techniques when designing similar systems—Typical PWR core case. *Ann. Nucl. Energy* **2011**, *38*, 1339–1346. [[CrossRef](#)]
46. Nickabadi, A.; Ebadzadeh, M.M.; Safabakhsh, R. A novel particle swarm optimization algorithm with adaptive inertia weight. *Appl. Soft Comput.* **2011**, *11*, 3658–3670. [[CrossRef](#)]
47. Boubaker, S.; Djemai, M.; Manamanni, N.; M'Sahli, F. Active modes and switching instants identification for linear switched systems based on Discrete Particle Swarm Optimization. *Appl. Soft Comput.* **2014**, *14*, 482–488. [[CrossRef](#)]
48. Arasomwan, M.A.; Adewumi, A.O. On the Performance of Linear Decreasing Inertia Weight Particle Swarm Optimization for Global Optimization. *Sci. World J.* **2013**, *2013*, 860289. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
49. Fan, S.K.S.; Chiu, Y.Y. A decreasing inertia weight particle swarm optimizer. *Eng. Optim.* **2007**, *39*, 203–228. [[CrossRef](#)]
50. Jayawant, P.; Glavin, K. Minimum spanning trees. *Involvo. A J. Math.* **2009**, *2*, 439–450. [[CrossRef](#)]

51. Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark (DTU Wind); The World Bank Group Global Wind Atlas. Available online: <https://globalwindatlas.info> (accessed on 25 January 2024).
52. GEBCO Compilation Group. GEBCO 2022 Grid. Available online: <https://www.gebco.net/data-products/gridded-bathymetry-data/gebco-2022> (accessed on 25 August 2023).

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.